

#nttw3

How did this happen?

A 5 minute presentation
@dericed 2018-10-26 #nttw3

Sponsorship:

reto.ch	
Axiell	
Open Broadcast Systems	
The Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision	
International Federation of Film Archives	
Centre national de l'audiovisuel (CNA)	
	€6,000.00

Expenses:

Travel grants	€1,200.00
Printing	€400.00
Organizer Travel/Lodging	€2,200.00
Dinner	€1,700.00
Total	€5,500.00

Other Contributions

MediaArea	Coordination, administrative support
British Film Institute	Conference Space, Technical Support, Breakfast, Lunch, Snacks
Organizers, Presenters, and Volunteers	Time
In-person Attendees	Travel, Lodging, and Related Costs
Remote Attendees	☹️
Community	❤️

#nttw4?

How will that happen?

Thanks!

